

METHODOLOGICAL AND LOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. The article examines modern pedagogical technologies, active and interactive forms and methods of teaching that contribute to the development of professionalism of future teachers. Particular attention is paid to the organization of micro-teaching, the use of the case method, and independent work of students in the electronic educational environment Moodle.

Keywords: competence, methodological and mathematical training of students, competence-based approach, state standards.

INTRODUCTION

The main trend in the development of higher professional education in recent years has been the implementation of a competency-based approach. This has become the main direction in the development of state standards for teacher training in various countries that have joined the Bologna process, including Uzbekistan. Analysis of competency-based models of graduates has shown that they clearly define the educational outcomes, in accordance with which universities develop substantive and technological aspects of teacher training. Such outcomes primarily include various general cultural and professional competencies [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Despite the fact that the concept of "competence" is used in state standards and has become firmly established in scientific usage, there is no unambiguous interpretation of it. Here are the most common definitions of this concept.

- The ability to apply knowledge, skills, and successfully act on the basis of practical experience in solving general problems, also in a certain broad area; a person's ability to apply knowledge, skills, and personal qualities for successful activity in a certain area; the ability to apply knowledge, skills, abilities, and personal qualities for successful activity in various problematic professional or life situations.
- Knowledge and experience in a particular area; knowledge and understanding of how to act in various professional and life situations.
- A range of issues in which someone is well informed.

- Readiness to effectively mobilize internal and external resources to achieve a set goal; readiness for successful activity in order to meet individual and social needs, constituting a social order for the education system.
- A set of knowledge, skills, abilities and methods of activity necessary for high-quality productive activity after training.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the above definitions, as well as the characteristics of the competence-based approach to teacher training proposed by the authors, shows that in the professional training of future teachers it is necessary to take into account such significant characteristics of the formed competencies as their universality, metadisciplinarity, integrativeness, activity-based nature, focus on the application of knowledge and skills in real practical activities [2].

A scientific problem is also the definition of the types of competencies, as well as the compilation of their specific list taking into account the direction of higher professional education.

Thus, the general approach is to highlight the competencies that characterize the general pedagogical training of graduates, and competencies related to a specific specialty or profile of the bachelor's degree program.

In our opinion, the full implementation of the competence-based approach in the training of primary school teachers requires taking into account the specifics of his professional activity, primarily, multi-subjectivity. In the conditions of work in a small school, other subjects (physical education, music, computer science, and sometimes a foreign language) are added to the traditional subjects for the teacher, since there are no subject teachers in a small rural school.

An important feature of the work of a primary school teacher is that he solves not only the problems of teaching primary school students various subjects, but also the problems of their personal development, the formation of educational activity as the leading one in primary school age (the ability to learn, universal educational activities) by means of various subject content.

This determines the need to ensure in university education not only a multidisciplinary training of students at a sufficiently high scientific level, but also their polymethodical training, as well as strengthening its integrativeness.

At present, when the competence approach has already become the main characteristic of university standards, it is important to determine the possibilities of each discipline in its implementation and specific ways of

forming various competencies in students. To do this, it is necessary to solve several significant scientific and practical issues:

- create a model of a graduate, i.e. "a comprehensive integral image of the final result of education", taking into account the specifics of his future professional activity, including determining "what a specialist is suitable for, what functions he is prepared to perform and what qualities he possesses" [3];

- taking into account the metadisciplinarity of competencies, determine the role of various disciplines in the formation of each competence;

- after determining the set of competencies that should be formed within the framework of a given discipline, it is necessary to decompose the competencies [4], i.e. identify their components, and on this basis determine the goals and objectives of the course;

- develop the main directions and methods of forming the identified competencies in students;

- create control and measuring materials and methods for diagnosing the planned learning outcomes in the discipline.

CONCLUSION

Since the competence-based approach assumes a focus on the result, it is necessary to provide methods for assessing its achievement. A rating system for assessing the quality of students' training plays a major role in this. The teacher develops a rating plan for the discipline, which contains a list of student activities during the semester in the main sections of the course and an indication of the forms of current and midterm control. Both classroom and extracurricular independent work can be assessed. The points scored are taken into account when assigning a grade for the exam. In our opinion, it is necessary to restructure the forms of student assessment at the exam according to subject methodology. To diagnose the development of individual competencies, it is envisaged that the student not only presents theoretical material, but also completes practical assignments, solves methodological problems, which allows assessing the level of practical training.

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